

EARTH SCIENCES

CHANGES IN THE MAIN CHARACTERISTICS OF THE ENVIRONMENT BASED ON THE EXAMPLE OF A SUSTAINABLE GREEN ECONOMY

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Abstract

Over the past decade, the sharp increase in human industrial and everyday activities has led to a rise in energy consumption, resulting in the release of harmful substances into the atmosphere. These substances often undergo transformation, spread over long distances, and pollute the environment, creating the risk of disrupting the Earth's energy balance and hindering sustainable environmental development. Rational use of natural resources will significantly reduce negative environmental impacts. Consequently, it will accelerate the implementation of appropriate practices in clean consumption and production, attract green investments, create new green jobs, slow environmental degradation and depletion of natural resources, and significantly contribute to improving public welfare.

Keywords: sustainable development, green economy, impurity transport, physical model, mathematical model.

1. Introduction

We attempted to model the movement of harmful substances in the environment using a physico-mathematical model. Initially, we briefly discuss the factors identified based on the physical model. Environmental pollution by harmful substances depends on many factors, including the source of pollution and emission volume, as well as meteorological factors such as wind speed, atmospheric stratification, terrain orography, surface characteristics, the magnitude of the turbulent field, and others. Therefore, meteorological factors are of great importance in constructing a physical model of impurity transport. Harmful substances are mainly emitted into the lower layers of the atmosphere—the troposphere (up to approximately 8 km above the

Earth's surface), where gases are well mixed. Subsequently, under the influence of local circulation, impurities move into the upper atmospheric layers. When constructing the mathematical model of impurity transport, the problem is mainly based on the physical model of the process. In studying the issue, we considered meteorological parameters, specifically wind speed in a turbulent environment. For passive impurities, the case is considered where impurity distribution occurs over a large area, where concentrations are averaged, and the height at which mass exchange approaches zero is analyzed (Fig. 1).

For calculations, the assumption was made that the total mass exchange approaches zero. A settlement (city) with an area equal to F (m^2) is considered. For our

example, a city with area F is selected. Harmful substances are emitted from various sources within the city at a rate G_{zn} (kg/s). The city is dominated by east–west winds with an average speed (m/s). The city width B

(m) is taken perpendicular to the wind direction. The volume of the studied object is considered, with height H. Within this volume, the mass concentration of harmful substances is denoted as C.

$$\bar{C} = \frac{m}{\rho F H}$$

Where

ρ – is the average air density above the city, assumed constant during the process.

A linear law of concentration distribution inside the volume is introduced, meaning that at any height Z, impurity concentration C

$$C = \bar{C} + \frac{C_0 - C_H}{2} - (C_0 - C_H) \frac{Z}{H}$$

is determined by a formula. Where:

C_0 – is the concentration of harmful substances at ground level;

C_H – is the concentration at height Z;

$C_H \infty \bar{C}$ These are related by an equation

$$C_H = \bar{C} \left[2 - \frac{C_0}{\bar{C}} \right]$$

A is perpendicular to the wind direction.

4. We consider the volume of the study object, the height of which is equal to H, the weight concentration of harmful substances in this volume is denoted by C.

$$C = m \rho F H$$

Where:

ρ is the average air density above the city, we assume that it is unchanged in the process.

5. We introduce a linear law of concentration distribution within the volume, which means that at any height Z, the concentration of the impurity C is considered by the formula:

$$C = C + C_0 - CH \frac{2 - (C_0 - CH)ZH}{H}$$

where:

C_0 – is the concentration of harmful substances at the ground surface

CH – is the concentration of harmful substances at a height H;

CH and C are related to each other by the equation:

$$C_H = \bar{C} \left[2 - \frac{C_0}{\bar{C}} \right]$$

$$\frac{C_0}{\bar{C}}$$

Let us assume that the ratio of concentrations in the process is constant

6. The specific flow of harmful substances above the city at a height H is determined by the well-known law of diffusion:

Where:

β – is the diffusion coefficient,

ρ_z – is the air density at a height H

At height H the total mass transfer is equal to 0. i.e.

harmful substances move vertically and are compensated by clean air moving in the opposite direction. $gz = CpWx$

accordance with the above, we turn to the **mathematical model**: when compiling the vertical displacement model, preference was given to the law of conservation of mass proven in thermodynamics, according to which the time variation of harmful substances in the system under consideration is equal to the difference between the flows entering and leaving the system.

$$dMdt = G_0z - gzF - gxBH$$

$$\frac{d(\bar{C} \rho F H)}{dt} = G_0z + \beta F \rho_H \frac{\partial C}{\partial z} - \bar{C} \rho \bar{W}_x B H$$

If we take into account that

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial z} = - \frac{C_0 - C_H}{H}$$

$$\frac{\partial \bar{C}}{\partial z} = \frac{G_0z}{\rho F H} - \frac{\beta \rho_H (C_0 - C_H)}{\rho F H^2} - \frac{\bar{C} \rho \bar{W}_x B}{\rho F}$$

If we introduce the notation:

$$\frac{d\bar{C}}{dt} = A - B\bar{C}$$

Where:

$$A = \frac{G_0z}{\rho F H}$$

$$B' = \frac{\beta B}{\rho F} \bar{W}_x + \frac{\beta \rho_H}{H^2} \left[\frac{C_0}{\bar{C}} - \frac{C_H}{\bar{C}} \right] \delta \delta$$

$$B' = \frac{\beta}{\rho} \frac{B}{F} \bar{W}_x + \frac{\beta \rho_H}{H^2} \left[\frac{2C_0}{\bar{C}} - 2 \right]$$

We have obtained a differential equation, the integral of which gives us:

$$C = AB' + C' - AB'C - Bt$$

Where, C' – average concentration of the pollutant at the beginning of the process.

C – average concentration after the first period of time t.

It is worth noting that over a long period of time the second part of the solution becomes equal to 0. The concentration takes on some maximum value, which is equal to:

$$C_{\infty 0} = \frac{A}{B'} = \frac{G_0z \left(\frac{C_0}{\bar{C}} \right)}{\rho F H \left[\frac{\beta B}{\rho F} \bar{W}_x + \frac{\beta \rho_H}{H^2} \left(\frac{2C_0}{\bar{C}} - 2 \right) \right]}$$

And at high altitude, in the H boundary zone, the formula takes the form:

$$C_0 \infty = 2G_0z \rho H^2 B W^2$$

Where

$\rho=1.2\text{kg/m}^3$. COC is taken equal to the average of 2,

H_0 is the height above which the air can be considered conditionally clean

$$H_0=100+500m.$$

B – width of the city in meters (3000-5000)m

W_x – average wind speed in m/s

$Co_z=3+6$ kg/min for gases emitted from the energy sector.

The weight of combustion products is equal to $Co_z=\rho \cdot 103\text{mg/m}^3$.

According to the experimental data, the concentration measured at a height of 2 m in the city of Kutaisi is 3.08 mg/m^3 , while the concentration obtained by the formula is 2.82 mg/m^3 , with an error of 0.82%.

The data obtained by the formula at and above 100 m altitude are presented in the graph (Fig. 2).

The formula is fair for passive impurities, but it is not general. Further refinement of the formula requires consideration of other additional conditions.

Conclusion

The existing model makes it possible to determine the dynamics of harmful substance transport. The model is significant because environmental pollution by impurities is one of the factors hindering sustainable environmental development. The development of a green economy contributes to improving environmental conditions and ensuring healthy living, supports the implementation of European standards and requirements in managing and implementing industrial processes, and fulfills the main requirement of sustainable development—significant improvement in the population's quality of life. The advantages of sustainable development principles and support for green economy development are emphasized in Georgia's current socio-economic strategic development plans.

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